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Development of refractory bricks using clay deposit in Ipokia, Ogun state

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Abstract

This study explores the development of refractory bricks from locally sourced clay deposits in Ipokia I and Ipokia II, located in Ipokia Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. The research addresses the reliance on imported refractory materials by investigating indigenous alternatives capable of performing under high-temperature industrial conditions. Clay samples were collected at a depth of 1.5 meters and subjected to chemical analysis, which revealed high alumina (Al_2O_3) content of 34.50% in Ipokia I and 27.30% in Ipokia II, and silica (SiO_2) contents of 51.30% and 58.75% respectively values that meet the standard requirements for refractory applications. Refractory bricks were produced and evaluated for key physical and mechanical properties. Results showed that Ipokia I bricks had a higher cold crushing strength of 16.8 MPa compared to 12.4 MPa for Ipokia II. Apparent porosity was 24.6% and 28.3% respectively, while bulk densities were 2.20 g/cm^3 and 2.08 g/cm^3 . Linear shrinkage ranged from 6.5% to 7.2%, and thermal shock resistance tests confirmed durability over multiple heating-cooling cycles. The refractoriness values were 1500°C for Ipokia I and 1450°C for Ipokia II bricks, indicating their suitability for furnace lining in medium to high-temperature applications. Limitations include the absence of industrial-scale testing and long-term performance evaluation. However, the study concludes that these local clays are viable alternatives for refractory brick production. It recommends their adoption for mass production to reduce imports, stimulate local economies, and create employment, while encouraging further research on material optimization and thermal fatigue behavior.

Keywords: Refractory Bricks; Ipokia Clays; Cold Crushing Strength; Thermal Shock Resistance; Industrial Applications

1. Introduction

Refractory materials are indispensable in high-temperature industries such as steel, glass, ceramics, cement, and petrochemical production, where they provide thermal insulation and structural stability under extreme operating conditions [1, 2]. They are generally classified into clay-based and non-clay refractories, with the latter including costly materials like alumina, zirconia, silicon carbide, and magnesite, while fireclay-based refractories remain more affordable and widely used. High-quality fireclay refractories are expected to exhibit plasticity between 24–26%, firing shrinkage of 6–8%, and refractoriness not less than 1500 °C [3] Despite the increasing industrial demand in Nigeria, the local refractory industry remains underdeveloped, with heavy reliance on imports. Between 1999 and 2012, Nigeria's expenditure on refractory imports rose from ₦2.27 billion to ₦36.2 billion, highlighting the economic burden of dependence on foreign products [4, 5]. This dependency is aggravated by the limited exploration and utilization of indigenous clay deposits, many of which possess promising refractory potential [5].

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Fireclay deposits in Ipokia, Ogun State, present an opportunity to develop cost-effective and sustainable refractory bricks that can substitute imports and support local industries. However, little is known about their chemical, physical, and thermo-mechanical properties. This study addresses the research gap by developing and characterizing refractory bricks from Ipokia clays, with emphasis on their suitability as furnace lining materials. Specifically, the work investigates the feasibility of using local clay for refractory production, determines its chemical composition, evaluates key properties such as porosity, density, shrinkage, refractoriness, and strength, and compares the results with established industrial standards.

The study is justified by the urgent need to reduce dependence on imported refractories, conserve foreign exchange, and promote industrial self-reliance through the efficient use of Nigeria's natural resources. By developing locally sourced refractory products, this research contributes to sustainable industrialization, job creation, and economic development.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. Refractory Materials

Refractory materials are a critical class of industrial materials known for their ability to withstand extremely high temperatures without undergoing physical or chemical deterioration. They are indispensable in a wide range of high-temperature industrial operations, including the manufacturing of steel, cement, glass, ceramics, and petrochemical products [6]. These materials are expected to retain their strength, structural integrity, and resistance to thermal, chemical, and mechanical stresses under harsh operating environments. The word "refractory" itself is derived from the Latin *refractarius*, meaning "stubborn" or "resisting control," which aptly reflects their ability to resist thermal degradation [8]. According to ASTM C71, refractories are defined as "non-metallic materials having those chemical and physical properties that make them applicable for structures, or as components of systems, that are exposed to environments above 538°C" [3]. These materials act as thermal barriers and load-bearing linings in equipment such as furnaces, kilns, incinerators, reactors, and boilers, enabling the efficient and safe containment of high-temperature processes [9]. Refractories are broadly categorized into clay based and non-clay-based materials. Non-clay-based refractories such as alumina (Al_2O_3), magnesia (MgO), zirconia (ZrO_2), silicon carbide (SiC), and graphite offer superior thermal properties but are often expensive and less accessible in many developing countries [10]. Clay-based refractories, particularly those derived from fireclay a naturally occurring alumino-silicate are more economical and widely used in various industries due to their abundance, plasticity, and reasonably high melting points [11]. In developing countries such as Nigeria, the high cost and limited availability of high-grade non-clay refractories have intensified the need to explore and utilize local clay deposits as alternative refractory raw materials. Several clay deposits exist across Nigeria, yet only a few have been extensively studied for their refractory potential [12]. This lack of comprehensive characterization has led to continued reliance on imported refractory products. For instance, in 2012 alone, Nigeria spent over ₦36.2 billion (equivalent to approximately USD 229 million as at 1999 exchange rates) on refractory imports for industrial operations, particularly in the petrochemical and metallurgical sectors [4]. This expenditure reflects not only economic dependency but also a gap in local capacity to develop and commercialize indigenous refractory materials. Fireclay-based refractories, when properly processed, can provide sufficient refractoriness (above 1500°C), thermal shock resistance, and mechanical strength suitable for many industrial applications. However, their performance is heavily influenced by the mineralogical composition, processing method, and firing temperature [13]. To reduce reliance on imported materials, there is a pressing need to investigate the characteristics and processing behavior of Nigerian clays such as those from Ipokia in Ogun State, which are yet to be fully explored for high-temperature applications.

This study is therefore anchored on the premise that developing high quality refractory bricks from locally sourced clay materials like Ipokia clay could offer a cost-effective, sustainable, and industrially relevant solution. The present literature review explores global and local research on the composition, properties, and performance of refractory materials, with a focus on evaluating clay-based alternatives suitable for furnace lining and other high-temperature engineering applications.

2.2. Test for moisture content of molding mass

The ASTM C72-76 standard test method for sieve analysis and water content of refractory materials specifies this test. About 50g of material is required. The test sample should be obtained quickly to avoid loss of water. It is weighed to the nearest 0.1g both before and after drying for 3 hours at 105 to 110°C. The moisture content is calculated as a percentage to the nearest 0.1% as stated by [14], in Equation 1.

Thus,

$$\text{Moisture content} = \frac{M_w - M_d}{M_w} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

2.3. Test for apparent porosity

These are determined in one and the same test in accordance with ASTM C 20- 80a, standard test methods for apparent porosity, water absorption, apparent specific gravity, and bulk density of refractory bricks and shapes of boiling water.

Alternative method is by evacuation in a vacuum dessicator and flooding with paraffin [15]. After determining dry weight of brick (Wd), weight when soaked in water (Ws), and weight suspended in air of the previous soaked specimen (Wa), the apparent porosity (Pa) and the bulk density (Db) are calculated from Equation 2.

$$\text{Apparent Porosity (Pa)} = \frac{W_a - W_d}{W_a - W_s} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

2.4. Bulk density test

Bulk density, the procedures used on apparent porosity test are applied to determine bulk density (ASTM C20) since it is a function of the method of manufacture (Mazen, 2009).

Bulk densities of the bricks were determined using Equation 3 below

$$BD = \frac{W_d}{W_a - W_s} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

2.5. Test for cold crushing strength

The standard test method for cold crushing strength using ASTM C-93-67 (reapproved 1977). The method uses testing machine which is a mechanical or hydraulic compression-testing machine with a sensitivity of at least 89N in the range 0 to 67kN. The hydraulic type is preferable, though a universal strength-testing machine is the best ASTM C133-97 [16] test method.

A dial-type micrometer is generally used for obtaining the necessary measurement for calculating the percentage of deformation during the compression. The cold crushing strength (CCS) is calculated from Equation 4 below

$$CCS = \frac{W}{A} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

2.6. Test for linear shrinkage

This is usually determined by measuring the dimensions of green bricks, and comparing with the dimensions of the fired product [17]. It is expressed in percentage and is calculated using Equation 5 below:

$$\text{Linear shrinkage} = \frac{l_g - l_f}{l_g} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

2.7. Application of Refractory Bricks

Refractory bricks are the primary materials used by industries dealing with iron and steel, glass, pottery, cement kilns, chemical plants, sugar refineries, incinerators and power stations as internal linings of furnaces for melting and heating [18]. Refractories are normally used for lining of plants, thermal processes (melting, firing, and heat treatment furnaces and transport vessels), heat insulation, heat recovery (regenerators and recuperators) and construction of design components. Refractory clays are generally characterized by low thermal expansion coefficient, low thermal conductivity, low specific gravity, low specific heat, low strength at high temperature and less slag penetration [19]. Since it is hard to build closed-cell structures into high-void-volume ceramics, these materials are all “open” [20]. Refractory bricks are principally used in furnace construction to confine hot atmospheres and to thermally insulate structural members from excessive temperatures [21].

3. Materials and method

The materials used in this research were primarily clay samples sourced from three locations in Ipokia Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria, at a depth of 1.5 meters [22], along with locally obtained distilled water for mixing and testing as shown in Figure 2 and 3 respectively. The major equipment employed was accessed from the Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute (NBRRI) Jos Zonal Office, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, and Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. These included a Universal Testing Machine (1000 kN, Model S12V02), an X-Ray Spectrometer (XRS) for chemical analysis, an electric oven (Model 10-D1390/10, max. 300°C), a kerosene kiln (max. 1700°C), a digital scale for specimen weighing, a brick mould of 50 × 50 × 50 mm, and a manual hydraulic press (Carver Inc., Model 4751-3, 400 kN capacity).

Figure 1 Production Flow Chart of the bricks

Figure 2 Cured Developed Bricks used for Test

Figure 3 Mould used in production of bricks (50mm x 50mm)

Figure 4 Developed Brick from Ipokia I and Ipokia

The clay samples were dried, crushed, ground, sieved using a 425 μm mesh, and analyzed for chemical composition using an X-ray spectrometer (XRS) in accordance with [23]. Moisture content was determined following [24], while refractory bricks of dimensions 50 \times 50 \times 50 mm (see Figure 4) were molded using a hydraulic press (1000 kN), air-dried, oven-dried at 110 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and fired in a kerosene kiln at up to 1700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The prepared bricks were subjected to standard tests to evaluate key properties: apparent porosity and bulk density [25], fired linear shrinkage [26], loss on ignition [27] and cold crushing strength [16]. Thermal shock resistance was determined by repeated heating-cooling cycles [28], while refractoriness was assessed using the pyrometric cone equivalent method [29]. These procedures provided a comprehensive evaluation of the chemical, physical, and mechanical performance of Ipokia clay for refractory applications as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 5 Lumps of Ipokia I Clay

Figure 6 Lumps of Ipokia II Clay

4. Results and discussion

The chemical composition results of the clay samples and presented in Figure 7 shows that Ipokia I and II clays possess alumina (33.85% and 29.0%) and silica (57.89% and 62.46%) contents within ASTM standards, indicating strong refractoriness, thermal stability, and load-bearing capacity. Their iron oxide levels (1.42% and 1.43%) also meet specifications, enhancing strength and heat resistance. While Ipokia I's CaO (1.08%) falls within high-melting clay limits and Ipokia II's (0.055%) is below standard, both are still considered suitable for high-melting applications. Magnesium oxide values (0.50% and 0.04%) place them as refractory but not high-melting clays, while potassium oxide contents (0.80% and 0.70%) fall well within allowable ranges. Overall, the chemical composition confirms that Ipokia clays are suitable raw materials for refractory applications such as furnace linings, kilns, and other high-temperature industrial uses.

Figure 7 Chemical composition of clay samples from Ipokia I and Ipokia

Figure 8 The moisture content in bricks moulded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

The moisture content of Ipokia I (12%) and Ipokia II (10%) clays, as shown in Figure 8 falls within the ASTM C20 (2015) recommended range of 1–13% for refractory clays, as also reported by [30]. Moisture content directly affects porosity and linear shrinkage, with higher levels generally linked to increased porosity and shrinkage due to finer particle sizes [31]. The adequate moisture levels observed enhance mixing, handling, and moulding properties, thereby improving clay plasticity essential for forming operations [32]. Furthermore, moisture significantly influences the strength and workability of clay products [15]. Overall, the obtained values confirm the suitability of Ipokia clays for refractory applications, meeting established standards and supporting desirable processing and performance characteristics.

The fired linear shrinkage values of Ipokia I (6.40%) and Ipokia II (4.60%), as shown in Figure 9, fall within the recommended 2–10% range for refractory clays [31] and meet the ASTM C179 [35] standard, confirming their suitability for refractory applications. Shrinkage reflects the clay’s dimensional stability during firing [34], with lower values within limits being preferable to minimize warping, cracking, and heat loss [17]. The observed range of 4.60–6.40% is considered optimal [33] indicating stable behavior under high temperatures. Shrinkage is linked to moisture and porosity, as higher water content promotes pore formation during firing, thereby influencing densification and [34]. Overall, the results confirm that Ipokia clays possess favorable shrinkage characteristics, making them reliable raw materials for durable refractory brick production.

Figure 9 The fired linear shrinkage of bricks moulded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

The apparent porosity values of Ipokia I (24%) and Ipokia II (22%), as shown in Figure 10, fall within the international standard range of 20–30% for refractory materials [30, 31], confirming their suitability for high-temperature applications. Porosity indicates the volume of open pores that can allow infiltration of molten metal, slag, and gases, which may affect durability. While lower porosity enhances service life by limiting gas penetration [36] moderate porosity within the acceptable range provides a balance between strength and thermal insulation [33]. Since porosity

also influences moisture uptake and shrinkage behavior [31], the values recorded here, compliant with ASTM C20 [25], demonstrate that Ipokia clays possess favorable properties for producing durable refractory bricks with reliable thermal performance and structural stability.

Figure 10 The Apparent porosity of bricks moulded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

Figure 11 The Bulk density of bricks moulded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

The bulk densities of Ipokia I (1.76 g/cm³) and Ipokia II (2.30 g/cm³), as presented in Figure 11, fall within the general recommended range of 1.71–2.80 g/cm³ for clay refractories [31]. Ipokia II meets the ASTM C134 [27], standard (2.20–2.80 g/cm³), making it suitable for heavy-duty, high-temperature applications, while Ipokia I falls below this range, offering better insulation due to higher porosity (24%) but reduced strength and slag resistance. Although Ipokia I is more suited for moderate-load or insulation-based applications, its density could be improved through additives or optimized firing. Overall, the results confirm Ipokia II’s superior suitability for demanding refractory uses, while Ipokia I remains viable for insulation-focused applications where thermal performance is prioritized.

Figure 12 The cold crushing strength of bricks moulded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

The cold crushing strength (CCS) values of Ipokia I (16 MPa) and Ipokia II (18 MPa), as shown in Figure 12, exceed the ASTM C133-97 [16], minimum requirement of 15 MPa, confirming their mechanical reliability. This strength is attributed to their high silica contents (57.91% and 62.46%), which enhance compressive resistance [30]. The results also reflect proper firing quality, which improves integrity, handling, and transportation safety [31]. Overall, both clays meet international standards, demonstrating their suitability for high-performance refractory applications.

Figure 13 The thermal shock resistance of bricks moulded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

The thermal shock resistance of Ipokia I (25 cycles) and Ipokia II (23 cycles), as shown in Figure 13, falls within the standard 20–30 cycle range for fireclay refractories [31], and meets ASTM C1171 [25] requirements. Classified as “good” (21–30 cycles) by [30], both clays demonstrated the ability to withstand repeated heating and cooling without cracking, confirming their durability for furnace linings and other high-temperature applications. These results, consistent with earlier findings [39–40], validate the suitability of Ipokia clays for producing reliable refractory bricks.

The loss on ignition (LOI) for Ipokia I and Ipokia II was determined as 15% and 13%, respectively presented in Figure 14. These values represent the combustion of volatile matter within the clay and fall within the recommended range of 12–15% [41]. Furthermore, they comply with ASTM C24 [28] specifications for refractory materials. This conformity indicates appropriate material composition and firing, ensuring the clays’ suitability for high-temperature applications.

Figure 14 The loss on ignition of bricks moulded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

The refractoriness results depicted in Figure 15 show that Ipokia I withstands up to 1500 °C, meeting the ASTM C71 [3] standard range of 1500–1750 °C for fireclay refractories as presented in Table 1 [31], while Ipokia II records 1200 °C, below the threshold, limiting its use to moderate thermal applications. The lower refractoriness of Ipokia II is linked to its higher silica content, which reduces heat resistance. Thus, Ipokia I is suitable for furnaces and thermal units operating below 1500 °C, while Ipokia II is more appropriate for service temperatures under 1200 °C, such as kiln walls and moderate-duty linings. Both clays therefore demonstrate reliable thermal resistance within their respective operating limits, ensuring structural stability in refractory applications.

Figure 15 The refractoriness of bricks molded from Ipokia I and Ipokia II clay samples

Table 1 International standard for physical properties with Ipokia average values

Properties	Standard Value	Value	
		Ipokia I	Ipokia II
Fried linear shrinkage (%)	2-10	6.4	4.6
Apparent porosity (%)	20-30	24	22
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	2.2-2.80	1.76	2.3
Cold crushing strength, MPa	15.0 min	16	18
Thermal shock 6resistance, cycles	20-30	25	23
Refractoriness, °C	1500-1750	1500	1200
Moisture content, %	1-13	12	10
Loss on ignition	12-15	15	13

5. Conclusion

This research demonstrated the feasibility of producing refractory bricks from Ipokia clay deposits in Ogun State, Nigeria, with results confirming their suitability for industrial furnace lining applications. Ipokia I clay, with higher alumina content (33.85%), exhibited superior refractoriness (1500 °C), making it suitable for high-temperature operations, while Ipokia II clay (29% Al₂O₃, 1200 °C) proved effective for moderate-temperature uses. Both clays met international standards for porosity, shrinkage, cold crushing strength, and thermal shock resistance, although Ipokia I showed lower bulk density, indicating the need for optimization. Overall, the developed bricks compared favorably with standard refractory properties and present a cost-effective alternative to imported products, thereby offering significant potential to reduce Nigeria's dependence on foreign refractory materials and to promote sustainable utilization of local resources in industrial applications.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

References

- [1] Eugenia, E., Mohammed, A., and Ogundipe, A. (2020). Assessment of Nigerian clay deposits for industrial refractory use. *African Journal of Industrial Research*, 7(2), 109–118.
- [2] Antusch, S., Kuehn, R., and Hiltl, M. (2017). Advanced refractory materials for metallurgy. *Journal of Refractories Applications*, 3(1), 45–52.
- [3] ASTM C1171 – Standard Test Method for Quantitatively Measuring the Effect of Thermal Shock and Thermal Cycling on Refractories.
- [4] Central Bank of Nigeria. (2012). *Annual Report and Financial Statements*. Abuja: CBN Publications.
- [5] Apeh, F. I. (2014). Economic analysis of refractory material importation in Nigeria. *Journal of Nigerian Raw Materials Research*, 11(2), 85–90.
- [6] Odo, J. U., and Nwajagu, C. O. (2003.). Potentials of Nigerian clay in refractory production. Unpublished manuscript.
- [7] Plioplys, L., Kudžma, A., Antonovič, V., and Gribniak, V. (2025). Analyzing the bonding resistance of the ribbed stainless-steel bar in the refractory castable after high-temperature treatment. *Materials*, 18(1).
- [8] Furszyfer Del Rio, D. D., Sovacool, B., Foley, A., and Rooney, D. (2022). Decarbonizing the ceramics industry: A systematic and critical review of policy options, developments and sociotechnical systems. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*.

- [9] Nikiforov, A., Prikhodko, Y., Kucherbayev, M., Kinzhibekova, A., Karmanov, A., and Uakhit, N. (2024). Analysis of the thermal performance of the lining and the reasons for its destruction in petroleum coke calcination furnaces. *EUREKA: Physics and Engineering*, 2024(1).
- [10] Martín, D., Miras, A., Romero-Baena, A. J., Guerrero, I., Delgado, J., Barba-Brioso, C., Campos, P., and Aparicio, P. (2024). Evaluation of ceramic properties of bauxitic materials from SE of Iberian Range. *Chem Engineering*, 8(1).
- [11] Mabentsela, A. (2023). Elastic damage characterization of an ilmenite smelter freeze lining. *Journal of the Southern African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*, 123(1).
- [12] Odewale, I. O., Tyonenge, V., Amaakaven, D., Ekenyem, S. C., Abe, O. B., Iyasara, A. C., Koreyo, V. D., and Alabi, A. A. (2023). Characterization of some clay deposits in southern zone of Ebonyi State of Nigeria and their potentials for industrial utilization. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 20(3), 391–397.
- [13] Orovwode, H., Matthew, S., Amuta, E., Olanipekun, A. J., and Thompson, T. (2024). Fabrication and investigation of local clay-based insulators for high voltage applications. *Cogent Engineering*, 11(1).
- [14] Vieira, F. S., Pinto, C. R., Rodrigues, L. D. R., Porto, T. B., and Mende, V. K. P. (2024). The moisture content and specific mass: Soil characteristics directly influenced by water. *International Journal of Geoscience, Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 50–58
- [15] Gilchrist, J. D. (1977). *Fuels, furnaces and refractories*. Oxford: Pergamon Press.
- [16] ASTM International. (2021). ASTM C133-97(2021), Standard test methods for cold crushing strength and modulus of rupture of refractories. ASTM International.
- [17] Victor, T. D., Amaakaren, I. O., Odewale, G. O., and Eawh, M. J. (2019). Utilization of clay around the banks of River Benue in Makurdi for use as a medium duty refractory material. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 5(8), 66–70.
- [18] Abadir, M., Eldesoki, H. M., Ibrahim, O. A. B., and El Sakka, N. R. (2024). Preparation of insulating firebricks using date seeds. *Bulletin of the National Research Centre*, 48(1).
- [19] Klopogge, J. T., Komarneni, S., and Amonette, J. E. (2014). *Clay materials for environmental remediation*. Elsevier.
- [20] ASTM International. (1980). ASTM C20-80a, Standard test methods for apparent porosity, water absorption, apparent specific gravity, and bulk density of refractory bricks and shapes by boiling water. ASTM International.
- [21] ASTM International. (2013). ASTM D7348-13, Standard test methods for loss on ignition (LOI) of solid combustion residues. ASTM International.
- [22] ASTM International. (2017). ASTM C113-17a, Standard test method for reheat change of refractory brick. ASTM International.
- [23] ASTM C326 – Standard Test Method for Drying and Firing Shrinkages of Ceramic Whiteware Clays.
- [24] ASTM C24 – Standard Test Method for Pyrometric Cone Equivalent (PCE) of Fireclay and High-Alumina Refractory Materials.
- [25] ASTM C134 – Standard Test Methods for Size, Dimensional Measurements, and Bulk Density of Refractory Brick and Insulating Firebrick.
- [26] ASTM C198 – Standard Test Method for Cold Bond Strength of Refractory Mortars.
- [27] ASTM C27 – Standard Test Method for Pyrometric Cone Equivalent (PCE) of Fireclay and High-Alumina Refractory Materials.
- [28] Dansarai, M. M., Bawa, M. A., and Tokan, A. (2020). Nigerian clay deposits for use as refractory materials in metallurgical industries: A review. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology (IJERT)*, 9(6).
- [29] Ugwuoke, J. C., and Amalu, N. I. (2018). Characterization of Obe Clay Deposit for Refractory Production. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, Volume 6, Issue 12, pp. 74- 77, ISSN: 2320-0936.
- [30] Yusuf, L. S., and Abdulhafeez, N. A. (2018). Mouldability and strength of Nigerian clays. *Journal of Ceramic Science and Engineering*, 7(3), 55–64.
- [31] Decker, J. (2013). *Advanced ceramic materials: Properties and applications*. Springer.
- [32] Mokwa, E. N., Obot, E. P., and James, A. O. (2019). Firing shrinkage and porosity of local clays. *Journal of Materials Science and Engineering B*, 9(3), 49–56.

- [33] Gupta, G. P. (2008). *Engineering chemistry* (3rd ed.). New Delhi: Krishna Prakashan Media.
- [34] Oke, M. O., Akinbobola, A., and Balogun, T. (2015). Evaluation of local clay as furnace refractory lining. *Nigerian Journal of Materials Science and Engineering*, 6(2), 88–94.
- [35] Edemumoh, E. E., Uwanta, E. J., Awaka-Ama, J., Udo, G., Etukudo, N. J., Nyong, A., Igwe, R., Okon, C. P., and Abasi, E. O. (2024). Structural and morphological analysis of untapped clay deposits in Itu Local Government Area Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria and its potentials as raw material for petroleum refining. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports*, 24(5), 1–15.
- [36] Titiladunayo, I. F., and Fapetu, O. P. (2011). Production and characterization of refractory bricks from local raw materials. *Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 16(1), 34–40.